

THERMAL PROPERTIES OF RHDPE/EVA/EGGSHELL POWDER COMPOSITES: EFFECTS OF FILLER LOADING AND PVC-MA COUPLING AGENT

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ABSTRACT

High-density polyethylene (HDPE) constitutes a significant portion of post-consumer waste in the packaging industries. One possible solution for this problem is the recycling procedure by using recycled HDPE (rHDPE) as raw material. However, there are some disadvantages of PE which include low environmental stress cracking resistance and poor compatibility with various additives. There have been many efforts to overcome this matter by blending the PE with other polymers such as ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA). On the other hand, the production of chicken eggs on an industrial level leads to a considerable quantity of shell residue, which is considered as a waste. Eggshells have been listed worldwide as one of the worst environmental problems. Due to the high content of calcium CaCO₃ which is 95 % in the eggshell, the eggshell powder (ESP) may replace the traditional CaCO₃ or talc to be used as filler or reinforce to change the mechanical properties of the rHDPE composites. This study was to investigate the effects of poly(vinylchloride)-maleic anhydride (PVC-MA) as a coupling agent on the thermal properties of the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites. Composites samples were prepared with different ESP filler loading (5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 phr) and incorporating 6 phr of PVC-MA. The PVC chemically modified with MA through in-situ reaction, using benzoyl peroxide as an initiator. The thermal stability of the composites was investigated by the thermogravimetric and differential scanning analysis. The result indicated that the compatibilized composites had better thermal stability than uncompatibilized composites. The temperature of degradation of the composites increased about 25°C in comparison to the uncompatibilized composites, indicating that PVC-MA improved the thermal stability of the polymer. The results also indicated that the percentage of crystallinity of the compatibilized composites was lower than composites without coupling agent.

1 INTRODUCTION

New materials can be prepared by blending with new properties not found in pure polymers. Blends are capable of providing the required properties than synthesizing new polymers. Polymer blending has been recognized as an important route to novel and useful polymeric products with properties superior to those of the individual components. With increasing understanding of the science and engineering involved, polymer blend is expected to offer increasing contributions to the plastic industries [1].

High density polyethylene (HDPE) is having unique properties such excellent mechanical properties, ozone resistance, good electrical properties, and chemical resistance but has poor stress crack resistance. On the other hand, ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) is having high impact strength, stress crack resistance, good ageing resistance, low temperature flexibility, improved clarity, permeability to oxygen and vapours, high moisture absorption, and high electrical resistance. Blends of HDPE and EVA are a new class of thermoplastic elastomers, which couple the superior properties of HDPE and EVA and open up new avenues for the commercial use of these blends.

However, because of difference of chemical structure between HDPE and EVA, HDPE is difficult to compatibilize with EVA. Compared to HDPE, EVA is more polar and less crystalline due to polar vinyl acetate (VA) group and leads to better compatibility with polar polymers and fillers [2]. The common technique used is to add small amount of compatibilizer due to their ability to improve both physical and chemical interaction between the components [3]. The crystallization behavior affects the properties of polymer blends. Therefore, the thermal stability of polymer blends plays an important role in polymer processing. The degree of crystallinity and thermal degradation are among the most important parameters in characterizing semicrystalline polymers. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of PVC-MA as a coupling agent on the thermal stability of the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites using thermogravimetric and differential scanning analysis.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Recycled HDPE pellets with a melt flow index of 0.7 g/10 min (190 °C) and a density of 939.9 kg/m³ and EVA contains 6.5 wt. % VA, with melt index of 2.5 g/10 min (80 °C; 2.16 kg) and density of 0.93 g/cm³ was supplied from A.R. Alatan Sdn. Bhd., Kedah Darul Aman, Malaysia. The chicken egg shells were obtained from local food industry in Negeri Sembilan, Malaysia. After a cleaning and drying process, the chicken egg shells were grinded into powder; filler with an average particle size of 63 µm were selected through sieving analysis. A commercial maleic anhydride (MA) powder and polyvinylchloride (PVC) was purchased from MERCK company while dicumyl peroxide (DCP, purity 98%) used as an initiator was purchased from Aldrich, and its half-lifetime at the melt grafting temperature (175°C) was about 1.45 min.

2.2 Preparation of Eggshell Powder

The egg shells were washed and crushed into small pieces. Then they were dried in an oven at 80 °C until the weight is constant to evaporate all water. The dried egg shells were grinded to powder using kitchen blender, which is designated ESP. Sieve was used to obtain an average filler sizes of 63 µm. Eggshell powder was dried in vacuum oven at 80 °C till the constant weight to make it free from moisture as reported in Shuhadah et. al. [4].

2.3 Composite Preparation

For the composites preparation, the compounding of the blends was carried out by melt blending in an internal mixer (Plasticoder, Brabender). The rHDPE was first mixed in the internal mixer at 160 °C, 50 rpm for 4 min and then pre-weighed amounts of EVA, PVC, MA, DCP, and ESP were added to the mixer and the mixing process continued for a further 10 minutes. Each of the molten samples was compression molded into sheets with a thickness of about 2 mm using a hydraulic press at 160 °C for 2 minutes and cooled under pressure for 4 minutes. Table 1 presents the formulation and designation of the samples. It should be pointed out that all the formulations included a matrix of 50 phr rHDPE and 50 phr EVA. 6 wt. % of PVC and MA was added as coupling agent together with 1% DCP as radical initiator to the compatibilized blends.

Composite code	rHDPE (phr)	EVA (phr)	PVC-MA (phr)	DCP (phr)	ESP (phr)
rHDPE/EVA	50	50	-	-	-
rHDPE/EVA/ESP5	50	50	-	-	5
rHDPE/EVA/ESP10	50	50	-	-	10
rHDPE/EVA/ESP15	50	50	-	-	15
rHDPE/EVA/ESP20	50	50	-	-	20
rHDPE/EVA/ESP25	50	50	-	-	25
rHDPE/EVA/ESP5 _{PVC-MA}	50	50	6	1	5
rHDPE/EVA/ESP10 _{PVC-MA}	50	50	6	1	10
rHDPE/EVA/ESP15 _{PVC-MA}	50	50	6	1	15
rHDPE/EVA/ESP20 _{PVC-MA}	50	50	6	1	20
rHDPE/EVA/ESP25 _{PVC-MA}	50	50	6	1	25

Table 1: Formulation of rHDPE/EVA/ESP samples.

2.4 Thermogravimetry Analysis

Thermal stability of the composites was investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) by using a Perkin Elmer TGA instrument [Model: Pyris Diamond TG/DTA] from ambient to 700 °C at a programmed heating rate of 10 °C/min in nitrogen. A sample weight of approximately 10 mg was taken for all the measurements. The weight loss against temperature was recorded. Differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTG) of the composite was represented in terms of the first derivative plots of the TGA curves. The data points denote the weight loss/time against temperature at the specified heating rate.

2.5 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

The melting and crystallization behavior of rHDPE/EVA blends was evaluated using Perkin Elmer DSC thermal system USA. Samples were scanned at a heating and cooling rate of 10 °C/min in nitrogen atmosphere. Samples weighing about 5 mg were used for the DSC. The percentage crystallinity (X_c) of the rHDPE phase has been determined with the following equation given below;

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_m^0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where; ΔH_m is the heat of melting of the semi-crystalline rHDPE blends, and ΔH_m^0 is the heat of melting for 100 % crystalline rHDPE and has been taken to be 293 J/g [5].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermogravimetry Analysis (TGA)

The thermogravimetric curves of the composites prepared at 5, 15, and 25 phr filler loading with and without PVC-MA are presented in Figure 1(a) and (b). The TGA data corresponding to the 5wt% loss temperature ($T_{-50 \text{ wt.}\%}$), temperature at the maximum rate of weight loss (T_{max}), and the final decomposition temperature (T_{final}) obtained during the degradation stages for rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites are listed in Table 2. To better estimate the effect of ESP filler loading on the thermal stability of the composites, TGA curves of rHDPE/EVA matrix was also presented. It can be observed that during thermal degradation, there are two weight loss stages for rHDPE/EVA sample. The deacylation reactions of the EVA phase chain degrade first and then the rHDPE phase chains and the polyacetylene-ethylene chains formed in the first stage degrade in the following step [6]. There is no weight loss of rHDPE/EVA sample before the first stage where it remains stable between 25 to 200 °C. Then the first stage of weight loss occurred by slow rate decomposition roughly from 230 to 400 °C followed by faster decomposition of second stage of weight loss roughly from 450 °C until the sample is completely decomposed at 515 °C.

Meanwhile, the decomposition temperatures of rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites start at higher values at about 235°C. The thermal properties of the eggshell had been studied by Kang et al. (2010) who reported that the eggshell powder showed the first step of weight loss from 260 to 400 °C due to the CO₂ released after thermal degradation of the eggshell. However, it was difficult to observe an accurate position for this step because it overlapped with the major decomposition of rHDPE/EVA matrix [7]. The results shown in Table 2 indicate that the temperature at 50% weight loss increased along with increased ESP filler loading. Composites with 25 phr ESP loading exhibited highest temperature of 470°C at 50% weight loss. It can be observed that the temperature at the maximum rate of weight loss of the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites is higher than the rHDPE/EVA sample. The temperature at the maximum rate of weight loss of rHDPE/EVA is 460.35 °C. For the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites, the temperature at the maximum rate of weight loss increased to 476.63 °C, 490.92 °C, and 495.30°C when the amount of the ESP increased to 5, 15 and 25 phr, respectively. These results are confirming the reinforcing role of ESP filler in rHDPE/EVA composites. The addition of the ESP into the rHDPE/EVA matrix caused an increase in the thermal stability of the composites.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: TGA curves of (a) rHDPE/EVA/ESP and (b) rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites.

At similar ESP filler loadings, composites with PVC-MA exhibited slightly higher temperature at 50% weight loss compared to the composites without PVC-MA. The delayed of the materials decomposition might be due to addition of the coupling agent PVC-MA to the composites where the enhancement of the interactions between the matrix and filler components. In addition, the results show that the temperature of the maximum rate of weight loss of the rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites is higher than the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites. The temperatures at the maximum rate of weight loss of the composites are 492.74°C, 508.83°C, and 514.28°C, respectively. However, there is no significant change in the final decomposition temperature of the rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites compared to the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites. From the result, it can be concluded that the rHDPE/EVA/ESP with PVC-MA gives better thermal stability compared to the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites.

Blend composition	T _{-50 wt.%} (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	T _{final} (°C)
rHDPE/EVA	425.82	460.35	531.33
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-5	426.66	476.63	693.05
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-15	460.56	490.92	693.28
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-25	470.76	495.30	694.28
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-5 _{PVC-MA}	441.39	492.74	693.31
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-15 _{PVC-MA}	464.28	508.83	694.08
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-25 _{PVC-MA}	475.90	514.28	694.45

Table 2: Data for T_{-50 wt.%}, T_{max}, and the T_{final} of rHDPE/EVA/ESP and rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites at different ESP loadings.

3.2 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Figures 2 and 3 represent DSC thermograms of rHDPE/EVA along with its composites with and without coupling agent PVC-MA at different filler loading. The endothermic peaks represent the melting temperature of their crystalline phases. Melting temperature (T_m) and the percentage of crystallinity of the composites were determined from the DSC curves and listed in Table 3.

From Figure 2, for all the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites, there is a decrease in the size of the melting peaks as compared to the rHDPE/EVA blends. This might be due to the co-crystallization of rHDPE with part of EVA phase that is present in the composites. These factors would promote the formation of more defective crystalline structure that could melt at a lower temperature than that of unflawed crystals [8]. The single melting peak in rHDPE/EVA blends might be because of the disturbance of EVA structures due to presence of ESP and the partial miscibility of the rHDPE and EVA crystalline phase in their melt state [9,10].

The addition of ESP filler does not significantly influence the melting temperature. However, results from Table 3 show that the melting temperature is increasing with the increased filler loading. The melting temperature of rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites was larger than that of rHDPE/EVA. As the filler content increased to 5 phr, the melting peak temperature rose from 126.91 °C for rHDPE/EVA to 127.14 °C. The highest melting peak temperature was observed for rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites with 25 phr filler loading, which is 127.22 °C. Meanwhile, a decrease of percentage of crystallinity can be observed for the composites as filler loading increased. This may be due to the addition of ESP act as a restriction to the rHDPE/EVA segments mobility, obstructing them from obtaining a highly order structure, therefore % crystallinity of the composites decreased.

From Figure 3, rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites displayed higher melting temperature as compared to rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites without PVC-MA, even it is not vary much. Higher melting temperature of composites meant that thermal resistance is higher as elucidated by the DSC method. Besides, the composites showed a lower percentage of crystallinity, but still significant. This phenomenon maybe explained by the increase of crystallinity provided by the ESP filler particles, that

are acting as a nucleating agent, due to the transcrystallinity effect provided by the strong interaction between the ESP filler and the matrix in the presence of PVC-MA as coupling agent [11].

Figure 2: DSC curves of rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites with different of filler loading.

Figure 3: DSC curves of rHDPE/EVA, rHDPE/EVA/ESP and rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites.

Blend composition	T_m (°C)	Percentage of Crystallinity (%)
rHDPE/EVA	126.91	40.85
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-5	127.14	35.25
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-15	126.66	32.28
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-25	127.22	31.28
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-5 _{PVC-MA}	127.97	35.23
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-15 _{PVC-MA}	127.63	31.22
rHDPE/EVA/ESP-25 _{PVC-MA}	129.08	30.95

Table 3: Thermal DSC parameters for rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites and rHDPE/EVA/ESP_{PVC-MA} composites at different ESP loading.

4 CONCLUSION

The investigation on the effect of filler loading and coupling agent PVC-MA on the properties of rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites was done in this study. PVC-MA was used as the coupling agent for rHDPE and EVA matrix filled with ESP filler. The addition of ESP filler has increased the thermal stability of the rHDPE/EVA composites. The PVC-MA as a coupling agent with the presence of DCP as an initiator has improved the melting temperature and thermal stability to rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites. TGA curves showed that the eggshell powder improved the thermal stability of the rHDPE/EVA/ESP composites. Thus eggshell powder can be used as filler to replace commercial CaCO₃ and improve the properties of composites.

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